

Do new forms for peer review affect the quality of the review? A case study based on interviews and text analysis¹

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Abstract

The peer review system is under pressure as invited reviewers increasingly reject the review invitation due to time constraints. Therefore, it is needed to find alternative ways of reviewing that are less time consuming and at the same time producing high quality reviews. One of the proposed alternatives is the Peer Circle (PC), where a team of reviewers collectively evaluates grant applications. One of the PC team members starts with a structured review, and the other members are expected to comment only on those parts of the application they are familiar with, which is expected to save substantial time. At the same time, the evaluation should be comprehensive and detailed enough to have at least the quality of the conventional reviews. This paper reports parts of the results of the evaluation study which focus on a comparison between the two types of reviews and their quality.

Introduction

The quality and sustainability of grant peer are under pressure as research funders require large amounts of reviewers for reviewing proposals, but increasingly invited scholars reject the invitation mainly because of a lack of time. In the case we study in this paper, rejecting review invitations amounts to about 60%. Because of this strain on the system, alternative approaches need to be considered. Are there other models for organizing the review process in a less time-consuming manner that would solve this problem? And can this be done without compromising the quality of assessments?

In this paper we analyze an experiment with a alternative approach, the Peer Circle, that was tested between March and November 2022 at the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (AvH), a main research funder in Germany. The Peer Circle (PC) is a collaborative evaluation procedure. A PC consists of five to ten reviewers plus committee members from the same field, and together they review between 20 and 30 applications in two rounds. For each application, a PC member is designated as *first reviewer*, and said reviewer is expected to start the review process with a structured but comprehensive assessment. Other PC members are expected to review (only) those parts of the applications that they feel they can review given their expertise and experience. Finally, the reviewers are expected to comment on one another's (partial) reviews and comments. As not all PC members have to provide full reviews, the expectation is that the PC can recruit from a wider population of researchers (also less experienced) than in case of the traditional peer review. Inspecting the set of PC members

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confirmed this, as most PCs included some members who reviewed grant applications for the first time. Taken the variety of contributions together, the PC activities should produce high-quality and complete assessments of the applications.

This paper reports about some parts of the evaluation of the PC, which was designed as a multi-method research project to compare the Peer Circle with the conventional way of peer reviewing grant applications. The evaluation aimed at answering whether the PC indeed saves time, and whether the reviews were at least as good as the traditional peer reviews.² One would assume that different ways of evaluating results in different review reports, and in this paper, we answer the following question:

Do the PC reviews differ from conventional reviews, and how this is assessed by the participating PC members?

We answer this question using as a linguistic analysis of the review texts, and with the subjective assessments of the PC members based on interviews and a survey.

Approach

The Peer Circle was implemented for four different fields in two rounds in 2022. We compared the PC with the conventional peer review process in the same fields in 2021 and with similar (in terms of disciplinary culture) fields in 2022 and 2021 that used the conventional review process. The next figure shows the design. These field comparisons could only partly be implemented, due to the relatively low number of cases. However, as the experiment continues, this can be done more thoroughly in the next phase of the evaluation study.

Figure 1: The approach

Four different fields were selected for the experiment, and four comparable fields were selected as control cases. Table 1 shows the fields, the number of PC members, and the number of applicants involved.

In the PC experiment, 89 applications were evaluated, which would require 178 reviewers in the conventional approach (2 reviewers per application)³ but in the PC only 29 people were involved. We asked the PC members about their time investment, and it was considered reasonable, and the log file analysis supported this. Consensus existed that the PC in total

² In the evaluation more questions were addressed: (1) Is the quality of the resulting reviews at least equivalent to that of conventional reviews? (2) Does the interaction within the PC result in premature consensus, hindering critical consideration of the applications? (3) Do the reviewers and committee members perceive the PC as a better alternative? (4) Is the PC more efficient than the conventional approach? (5) Does the PC committee select the best applicants? (6) Do the PC reviews influence the gender balance in the selection outcome? Here we of course cannot present the answers on all these questions.

³ In practice, quite some reviewers send in their review too late or not at all, with the effect that only in 60% of the cases two reviews are available and in the other cases only one.

requires less time than the aggregated time for the conventional reviews. The analysis of the logfiles supported this (Van den Besselaar et al. 2023).⁴

Table 1. Numbers of applicants and of PC members

	2021	2022	2022
<u>Experimental fields</u>	Pre Peer Circle	Peer Circle	# PC members
Inorganic Chemistry	29	20	5
Materials Science	13	19	9
Zoology (biodiversity)	24	30	6
Modern & Contemporary History	32	20	9
<u>Control fields</u>			
Solid State Chemistry	21	14	
Materials Engineering	16	21	
Plant Science	15	19	
Ancient History	17	15	

Data

The following data were collected about the PC:

- Interviews: PC members and RFO staff were interviewed about their opinions about the PC, and on their (self-reported) PC behavior. In total 56 interviews were conducted.
- Survey: PC members were twice surveyed for similar information as was collected in the interviews, to have a more reliable measurement of opinions and behavior.
- Logfiles: These provided information about the online activities in the PC digital platform: Number of logins, time online, time active online, number and date of review contributions and of comments.
- Observational data from committee meetings: Time spent for each application, number of discussants for each application.
- Reviews: The conventional review texts and the PC reviews and comment texts were analyzed to identify what review dimensions were addressed and what scores were given. Also the style of the reviews were compared, using the LIWC tool.
- Administrative data: The committee scores the applicants received, and the decisions.
- Personal characteristics (from the application files): Age, nationality, gender, residence, institutional affiliation, planned host, current position.
- Bibliometric data measuring productivity and impact of the applicants.

Findings

In a conventional review, reviewers should address all aspects of the application, which requires a full understanding of all aspects of an application – which many reviewers do not have. In the PC, a member whose expertise is close to an application is designated as *first reviewer* for that application, and they are expected to address most of evaluation dimensions. The other PC members can add their review of parts of the application and can react to

⁴ Van den Besselaar P et al. (2023). *Evaluation of the 2022 Peer Circle experiment at the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation*. Amsterdam, TMC Research.

reviews and comments of the other members. Doesn't this lead to incomplete and unbalanced reviews?

The interviews and the survey showed that the large majority of the PC members found the reviews as *comprehensive* as the conventional reviews. Although the PC members were aware of the possibility of a too early consensus (due to mechanisms like group think), almost all found that this had not taken place – and they gave examples of discussions about differences in opinions. In fact, they found the PC reviews better than the conventional approach as the latter more often go into technical details in stead of assessing the overall value of a grant proposal. Furthermore, they found that PC reviews tended to be more balanced as they were based on input by more scholars than possible in conventional reviews.

In the interviews, many PC members found that the *level of depth and detail* was at least similar to the conventional peer review. That may not be the case for all evaluation comments individually, but the larger number of comments from multiple perspectives was seen as compensating for that. And the more people who view an application, the more objective the evaluation becomes and the better the overall judgement.

These opinions can be compared with the characteristics of the review texts. Level of *depth and detail* may relate to the length of the reviews, which differs between the conventional reviews and the PC review: The (one or two) conventional reviews together use 1253 words, whereas the PC review is 751 words on average. Conventional reviews are longer than the PC reviews, and interviewees suggested that this may be because several of the standard parts of the conventional review are lacking here, such as a summary of the proposed project and several courtesy formulations. Furthermore, interviewees mentioned that conventional reviews are becoming shorter too. However, the structure of both types of reviews is the same, covering four questions: (1) the quality of the CV, (2) the quality of the core publication, (3) the quality of the proposed project, and (4) the future perspective of the applicant. In table 2, we compare the total length of the four different parts.⁵

Table 2. Length of the review texts⁶

		Total*	CV	Core publications	Project proposal	Future potential
Conventional	Average	1253	347	292	422	192
	CoV**		0.48	0.59	0.52	0.52
Peer Circle	Average	751	200	141	311	99
	CoV		0.67	0.85	0.59	0.70
Ratio	Conventional/PC	1.67	1.74	2.07	1.36	1.94

* Sum of the number of words in the four core parts of the review. We did not include the summary texts and the profile texts, as these do not exist in the PC procedure.

** Coefficient of variance

The expectation articulated in the interviews was that the PC would focus less on the project proposal than in a conventional review, so one would expect that in the PC a smaller part of the text would be devoted to the planned project than in a conventional review. This, however, is not the case. In the conventional reviews, 34% of the text is devoted to the project proposal, in the Peer Circle this is 41%. One explanation for this could be that in the PC, part

⁵ We do not differentiate here between the two rounds, as the length was about the same in the two rounds.

⁶ In our comparison fields, using the conventional peer review approach, there were 235 applicants and about 100 had only one external reviewer. This illustrates the problem of finding enough reviewers. In some of those cases, when the committee member had the appropriate specialization, they were appointed as second reviewer. For the other cases we used the statements of the committee member for the analysis, even if they were not a formal reviewer. The summaries by AvH staff were not used in the text analysis.

of the words are used to explain the project to those PC members who are less familiar with the topic. Furthermore, the PC devotes fewer words to the core publications, and about the same share of the text on discussing the CV and future potential.

Although the structure of the two types of reviews is the same, some interviewees mentioned that the *writing style*⁷ in the PC reviews and comments is more informal than in conventional reviews. An interviewee noted that “the comments are open and honest”, and another interviewee called it “a less curated review, less effort to make a coherent argument that leads to the selected verdict”. The PC seems to have a social dynamic that is more openly and more honestly evaluating the grant applications. A first linguistic analysis of the review texts confirms these style differences, suggesting a different relation of the reviewers with the reviewed application: Reviews normally have a strong *analytical style* as opposed to a more narrative style, and this also holds for the conventional reviews in the here studied case. However, the PC reviews score somewhat lower on analytical writing. Another difference is that the conventional reviews score higher on the *clout* variable than the PC review, stronger emphasizing the dependence of the applicant on the reviewer’s verdict. Finally, the language of the PC review is more open than the language of the conventional reviews, indicating a higher level of *authenticity*.

Another question that can be tentatively answered by analyzing the review texts is whether PC reviews have similar emphasis on the various evaluation criteria as is observed in the conventional reviews. We created a ‘dictionary’ with the terms that relate to the evaluation criteria specified for the grant under study: career quality, mobility, independence, quality of the (core) publications, and school and university performance, quality of the project, quality of the host, and excellence. This was manually done using a term extraction of all the review reports, followed with a selection (by two researchers) of the relevant terms for each evaluation dimension. The review texts of the PCs were compared with those of the conventional review approach – not yet at the field level. Indeed some differences were found in the emphasis on the various criteria.

First of all, the PC reviews have a significantly higher share of *common words*, indicating that there are less technical terms in those reviews. This is in line with the expectation that the PC would focus less on the technical content, and more on the other evaluation criteria, something that was emphasized in several interviews. This is also consistent with the observation that the conventional review reports contain significantly more project-related words. In the conventional review, the reports focus more on performance than in the PC review, but the PC reviews focus more on the host and the independence of the applicant.

One of the criteria is the quality of key publications. Interviews with several PC members indicate that they scan the core publications rather than read them, and RFO staff members have also raised this issue in the interviews. Publications are discussed more in terms of numbers, journal impact, and citations than in terms of content and findings. Is this different from the conventional review process where specialist reviewers are selected for each application? Our data suggest not, and the relative frequency of the use of “bibliometric” terms in conventional reviews is similar to the use of those terms in the PC reviews.

⁷ Van den Besselaar P et al. (2018), Using linguistic analysis of peer review reports to study panel processes. *Scientometrics* 117, 313-329; Van den Besselaar P, & Mom C (2022), The effect of writing style on success in grant applications. *Journal of Informetrics* 16(2):101257; Van den Besselaar P (2022), Identifying gender stereotyping using text analysis. *In Proc. 26th STI 2022*

Observation of discussions in the selection committees suggests the same, and there too the quantitative properties of the publication lists are mentioned often.

Interviewing the PC members and the RFO staff, the interviewees felt that the PC reviews have good depth and scope, and that only the technical content of the applications is covered more in the conventional reviews. However, several interviewees welcome the reduced focus on technical content, as it prevents that technical details become too important in the review and the selection process. For reviewing papers this is important, as there the quality of technical aspects of the research is very critical. In assessing grant application, individual technical problems were considered less important, as during the research, problems can be solved, and technical weaknesses can be improved.

The opinions found in the interviews were supported by the survey, as almost all PC members tend to find the overall review result of high quality, find it at least as good as the conventional review procedure (Van den Besselaar et al., 2023). We should note here that there were also PC members not answering these comparative questions. This can be easily explained by the fact that for several PC members this was the first time they were reviewing grant applications and therefore could not compare their PC experiences with earlier conventional reviewing.

Conclusions and discussion

The aim of the PC experiment was to test whether less labor-intensive review models are possible and whether they can lead to high quality reviews. The evaluation conforms this. The PC seems to be saving time at the community level, and is also not overloading the PC members with work. PC members remarked that at the community level, the PC saves time.

At the same time, the PC members were satisfied with the quality of the PC reviews and even saw various advantages, such as there are more views on an application, that one is better able to differentiate between applications as one sees a few of them, and not only one as in the conventional review approach.

We found substantial differences between the two modes of reviewing, among others a different emphasis on the evaluation criteria, and – possibly more important – a different style indicating another relation between the reviewers and the reviewed. The style of the PC reviews seems to be less formal, and showing a more equal relation between reviewer and reviewed: and that seems to be more adequate if one takes the peer in peer review seriously.

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